

**THE LINGUOCULTURAL ASPECT OF
LEXEMES ILLUSTRATING THE
CONCEPT OF “APPEARANCE”**

Linguistics

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Abstract

The article interprets semantic and linguocultural properties of the lexemes expressing the concept of appearance on the examples of extracts from fiction texts in Uzbek and Russian languages. The author discusses the role of lexemes describing opinion in increasing the emotional expressiveness of literary texts.

A word expresses an exact meaning and demonstrates the idea. On top of that, as well as meaning and delivering one or another thought, it elucidates the characteristic of an action. This feature of a word can be particularly observed in its civilization until today. The words describing nature of characteristics can be met in books consisting of various contents. However, the ones in literary books have greater significance. The reason is that the words describing features are important in illustrating the contents of a literary book, increasing its emotional expressiveness, clarifying the objective of a book, describing national culture and depicting the plot along with the spiritual state of the characters. Therefore, an author selects and makes a good use of words which are suitable for the situation to describe characteristics.

Symbolize material and emotional object, event and action. It can be seen in the instructions or hints of an action and features of other objects. The concept of symbol is analyzed in philosophy, logics, linguistics, psychology and sociology which means it plays an important role in all sciences related to the investigation of human activity. There is a vital link between a symbol and the process of delivering information. A symbol consisting of one material object also depicts another object. The functions of a symbol are recognizing, showing differentiating and referring to a thing, sign or a hint. For instance, *the signs of a lost boy, the signs of a plant, to mark*. In order to draw the image and features of objects and actions, for example, these symbols can be used: *a black briefcase, an attractive girl* [3, p.38]. The lexemes in the Uzbek and Russian languages are divided into two parts. They are: 1. Lexemes depicting a human; 2. Lexemes describing different features of objects.

Lexemes describing features

1. Lexemes depicting a human;

1. Lexemes enlightening the appearance of human: *fine-boned, well-built, handsome, pretty, good-looking beautiful.*
2. Lexemes describing character: *taciturn, womanizer, wit, feuding, naughty, childish.*

3. Lexemes illustrating the spirituality of a person: *merry, unhappy, brokenhearted, blissful, guilty, contented*.

II. Lexemes describing different features of objects:

1. Lexemes describing colour: *black, white, red, pink*.
2. Lexemes illustrating flavor: *sweet, bitter, rotten, sour*.
3. Lexemes representing smell: *aromatic, stinking, malodorous, fragrant*.

In Russian literary books, words describing features are widely used, moreover they are comprised of some groups as in the Uzbek language:

I. Lexemes depicting human (лексемы, обозначающие признаки личности (людей)):

1. Lexemes enlightening the appearance of a human (лексемы, обозначающие внешний вид личности (человека)): *красивый (beautiful), крупный (fine-boned), хромой (lame), плечастый (wide-shouldered), высокого роста (tall), стройный (well-built), миловидный (sweet), прелестный (charming)*.

2. Lexemes describing personality: (лексемы, обозначающие характер личности (людей)): *умный (smart), добрый (kind), честный (honest), трудолюбивый (hard-working), хитрый (cunning)*.

3. Lexemes illustrating the spirituality of a person: (лексемы, обозначающие душевное состояние личности (человека)): *радостный (merry), грустный (sad), печальный (brokenhearted), виноватый (guilty), бодрый (hale and hearty), задумчивый (pensive)*.

II. Lexemes describing different features of objects (лексемы, обозначающие признаки предметов):

1. Lexemes describing colour (лексемы, обозначающие цвет): *чёрный (black), белый (white), жёлтый (yellow), красный (red), зелёный (green), синий (blue)*.

2. Lexemes illustrating flavor (лексемы, обозначающие вкус): *кислый (sour), горький (bitter), солёный (salty), сладкий (sweet), пресный (fresh), вкусный (delicious), не вкусный (unpalatable)*.

3. Lexemes representing smell (лексемы, обозначающие запах): *приятный (aromatic), вонючий (malodorous), зловонный (stinking), не приятный (unpleasing), благоухающий (sweet-scented), душистый (fragrant)* [1, p. 647].

The lexemes describing the concept of appearance defines external show, sensible phenomenon and view [4, p. 419]. The words that explain physical appearance of characters in fiction books are applied to depict them in details. While words like *a flower with birth-mark (norgul), wrestler (polvon), ogre-shaped or ogreish (devqomat), tall, hero, beautiful, lovely, pretty, appealing, attractive, good-looking, beautiful* emphasize on positive peculiarities of individuals, lexemes namely *whipped, lame, scraggy, plain, ugly* demonstrate negative aspects of the characters of a book. *Nigoroyim was a short, sallow-skinned woman with mesmerizing and*

almond-shaped eyes who would look even more beautiful without pale spots of rot on her cheeks [2, p. 317].

Abdulla Kadiri applied several lexemes to depict appearance of the characters in his books. For example, he used the word *beautiful* to describe Nigoroyim's appearance as well as adjectives, such as *naive*, *tolerant* and *literate* to show her personality.

While demonstrating what Solih mahdum looks like, the writer made use of a number of lexemes, for example *quite tall*, *muscular* or *fair-skinned*: *Mahdum was quite tall, muscular, and fair-skinned master with limp hair and a glowing face. He was above his age of 40, and had already had some gray hairs* [2, p. 315].

In addition, I would prefer to outline the linguocultural aspects and semantics of some words in the Uzbek and Russian languages like *good-looking*, *handsome*, *beautiful*, *pretty*, *fine-boned*, *attractive*, *appealing*.

Using words related to color and shape to describe appearance can be a great help for readers to create a full image of a character. Abdulla Kadiri depicted Rano in such a way: "... *this girl was created in the color of flower orchid or ivory. Her hair was brunette, so even if it seemed as dark as a night in shadow, in fact it appeared to be chestnut-brown in sunlight. It was also seen in her eyes: when she stared with her mesmerizing eyes, they shone brightly in such a different way. There was a circle of eyeshadow under his eyelashes. Even though her brows looked joined, these two brows were separated by a horizontal flow. Her nose was so proportional that it was impossible to criticize it, and there were few strands above her lips which were about to beam every time she felt embarrassed. Her complexion was neither long nor round. When she looked at somebody smiling, her lips in the colour of a red apple looked like a real orchid flower. Her hair was thick, and she was covered with her unnumerable braids. She was neither too tall nor short, and there were henna flowers on her ample little fingers...*[2, p. 120]. In this example, Rano's *beautiful*, *dark eyes*, and *glowing complexion* were described with the help of words describing feature.

The lexeme of *beautiful* was defined in four ways in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language:

1. Appealing, pleasing, very beautiful girl.
2. Having the qualities of beauty and attractiveness.
3. Merry, cheerful, delightful, mirthful.
4. *Beauty* – the first-name of females [4, p. 530].

Russian literary books also consist of many lexemes illustrating the appearance of individuals: *красивый* (*handsome*), *стройный* (*slender*), *сутулый* (*round-shouldered*), *храмой* (*lame*), *крупное телосложение* (*outstanding figure*), *высокий рост* (*tall*), *чёрные глаза* (*dark eyes*), *короткие волосы* (*short hair*), *приятный* (*pleasing*), *светлокожый* (*fair-skinned*) and so on. These words are used to describe positive image of characters.

The word *красивый* describes the person in a light color and means *handsome* or *beautiful*: *She was still beautiful even in her fiftieth. However, when she was young, when she was eighteen, she was stunning, tall, slender, graceful and majestic, particularly majestic.* The lexemes of *высокая* and *стройная* are used to describe that the character is *tall* and *slender*, moreover they indicate the author's attitude towards the character.

Authors in both languages use diverse lexemes to demonstrate the appearance, personality, spiritual state and shape of characters.

All in all, lexemes in the Uzbek and Russian languages which describe peculiarities function to clarify the idea of a novel, to fortify its emotional expressiveness, to demonstrate its moral significance, to deliver historic colouring, and to expand the readers' outlook.

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